

Biomechanical investigation and neuromusculoskeletal modelling of human movement in healthy adults (Griffith University ethics ref. no. 2017/521)**Research team contacts****Student researchers**

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Human gait, including walking and running, is dynamic and complex activity that can be altered by musculoskeletal injuries and disorders (pathological gait). Developing a complete understanding of the features of healthy human gait is a critical first step towards understanding how structural and functional limitations of pathological gait alter the movements and forces produced by the neuromusculoskeletal system and developing interventions to ameliorate these alterations. Many forces within the body, such as the forces of muscles acting on bones and forces experienced at the joints (joint contact forces), cannot be directly measured. To gain insight into these forces we can use neuromusculoskeletal modelling techniques.

The aim of this research is to collect information about healthy human gait. For the purposes of this research, healthy is defined as the absence of a) any musculoskeletal condition of the lower limb b) history of serious ligament injury to the lower limb c) contraindications for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Movement information will be collected through motion capture and lower limb skeletal and musculotendon structure and function will be collected through MRI and strength testing. This information will be used to construct neuromusculoskeletal models to discover how movement patterns of individuals with musculoskeletal disorders, such as anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) reconstruction or Femoroacetabular impingement (FAI), differ from those without these conditions. This will allow us to determine whether changes in neuromuscular control influences the forces acting on the lower limb during human gait.

Participation

We are seeking individuals without any musculoskeletal condition of the lower limb, such as osteoarthritis, with no history of serious ligament injury to the lower limb and without any metal implants to participate in this research. This is important to this research because we are trying to discover if people without lower limb injuries and musculoskeletal conditions like OA and FAI move differently to those without musculoskeletal conditions.

A verbal medical history questionnaire will be administered to determine if you suffer from any medical conditions, such as musculoskeletal, neurological or other health problems that may affect your ability to walk. If you identify as having a musculoskeletal conditions that will affect your ability to act as a 'healthy' control, to safely perform maximal muscle contractions, or if you have any contraindications for MRI (e.g. pregnancy or those who have metal objects embedded within their bodies) you will not be asked to participate in this research. If you are ineligible for this research but are still interested in assisting with our

research in the future, please let us know so that we can contact you again in future if a suitable project arises.

People can have conditions like FAI without having any symptoms (e.g. pain). De-identified MRI will be screened for signs of FAI and/or OA. If there is any reason to suspect that you have either of these musculoskeletal pathologies you will be informed of the possible presence of such pathology. We will provide you with a copy of the images for you to seek further assistance from your GP.

Expectations

If you choose to volunteer you will be asked to attend a motion capture at Griffith University Biomechanics Laboratory, located on the Gold Coast Campus, and an MRI session at Qscans radiology clinic in Southport. The motion capture and MRI will occur at a time convenient to you, but must occur on the same day. Transportation arrangements will be made for you to travel between the university and Qscans radiology clinic, Southport.

Griffith University Biomechanics Laboratory: At the Griffith University Biomechanics Laboratory, we will complete motion capture while you walk, run hop and sidestep, including muscle activation of your lower limb. Initially, you will be prepared for the functional assessments with the application of reflective markers and muscle activity (EMG) sensors. You will then be asked to perform trials of walking, running and sidestepping across an instrumented walkway containing a force platform. You may be asked to perform each of these tasks up to 4 times each. Subsequently, you will be asked to undergo strength tests on a dynamometer to measure the strength of your knee muscles. You will be placed in position with your leg strapped to the machine, from which you will then be instructed to push maximally against the machine or resist the movement of the machine. It is estimated that the assessments conducted at the Griffith University Biomechanics Laboratory will take approximately 3-4 hours.

Qscan: The purpose of your visit to Qscan is to acquire an MRI of the scans of the hip, knee and ankle joint and surrounding muscles. These images are important to create a neuromusculoskeletal model of the lower limb that is personalised to your musculoskeletal structure. The duration of the visit is typically up to 1 hour.

Expected benefits

We cannot and do not convey that there will be any benefits to you personally through your participation in this research. Your participation will assist with the identification of neuromuscular and biomechanical parameters that are associated with pathological gait for various conditions, including, for example, FAI or knee OA in people who have undergone ACL reconstruction. Understanding these mechanisms may help to facilitate the future development of strategies to improve surgical outcomes and/or ameliorate risks of development of OA. Consequently, by participating you will be providing valuable assistance to research that could benefit many others in the future.

Risks

None of the measurements or exercises performed will place you at any more risk than would be encountered during routine clinical tests, normal day-to-day living and sporting activities. However, a small potential remains for assessments involving running, sidestepping and maximal strength to result in musculoskeletal injury. Additionally, performance of the strength tests may result in some residual muscle soreness, although this will subside within a couple of days. To limit the possibility of injury, ample time is given for warm up prior to commencing tasks. Should a muscle strain occur, you will receive treatment for a sports injury advised to seek medical assistance from your GP who can refer you for further treatment.

Magnetic resonance (MR) and ultrasound imaging modalities do not use ionising radiation to capture images. MRI is not suitable for people who are pregnant or have metal objects embedded within their bodies such as pacemakers. Prior to MRI referral you will be asked to complete a questionnaire to confirm that it is safe for you to undergo MRI.

For the MRI you will be placed in the MRI scanner which has a diameter slightly wider than the body for up to an hour. During the scan the scanner can emit loud noises. You will have headphones to ameliorate the volume of these noises and the scan technician will be able to communicate with you during the scan to inform you when to expect loud noises and about how long the scan will take.

Confidentiality

The conduct of this research involves the collection, access and/ or use of your identified personal information. The information collected is confidential and will not be disclosed to third parties without your consent, except to meet government, legal or other regulatory authority requirements. A de-identified copy of this data may be used for other research purposes. However, your anonymity will at all times be safeguarded. For further information consult the Universities Privacy Plan at <http://www.griffith.edu.au/about-griffith/plans-publications/griffith-university-privacy-plan> or telephone the manager of research ethics (07) 3735 4375.

The data collected for the purpose of this study will be safely stored in research storage space (online) provided by Griffith University. Access to this data will not be provided to anyone outside the research team. All participant sheets and MRI discs containing participant information will be retained safely in a locked cabinet. After a period of five years, all data will be transferred to Research Vault, which is a service offered by Griffith University for long term storage. Participant sheets and MRI discs will be destroyed after a period of five years.

No study or published document will identify you personally and it will not be possible for a third party to identify you from these publications. The motion capture system used in this research to record your movement only tracks the markers affixed to your skin. It is not possible to identify your image from the recordings. Upon email request, a simplified summary of the results obtained during your data collection session will be provided for your reference.

Consent to participate

Your Participation in this project is entirely voluntary. You are free to deny consent before or during the experiment without prejudice or penalty. In the latter case, such withdrawal of consent will be at the time you specify and not at the end of a particular trial.

Your participation or withdrawal of consent will not influence your present and/or future involvement with Griffith University. In the case of student involvement, it will not influence grades awarded by the University. You have the right to withdraw from any experiment, and this right shall be preserved over and above the goals of this experiment.

If you choose to participate, we would like to ask you to sign a written consent form (attached) to confirm your agreement to participate.

Questions / further information about the project

Questions concerning the procedures and or rationale used in this investigation are welcome at any time. Please ask for clarification on any point you feel is not explained to your satisfaction. Your initial contact person is Bryce Killen.

Concerns / complaints regarding the conduct of the project

Griffith University is committed to researcher integrity and the ethical conduct of research projects in accordance with the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research. However, if you do have any concerns or complaints about the ethical conduct of the project you may contact the Research Ethics Officer on (07) 3735 4375 or research-ethics@griffith.edu.au, quoting the GU ethics reference number for the project (GU ref no: 2017/521). The Research Ethics Officer is not connected with the research project and can facilitate a resolution to your concern in an impartial manner.

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Statement of Consent

By signing below you are confirming that you:

- Have read and understood the information document for this project
- Understand that your involvement will include a MRI, functional assessments including strength, walking, running, side stepping and balance and monitoring of your physical activity.
- Have had any questions answered to your satisfaction
- Understand the risks involved
- Understand that there is no direct benefit to you for your participation
- Understand that participation is voluntary
- Understand that if you have any additional questions you can contact the research team
- Understand that you are free to withdraw at any time without comment or penalty
- Understand that you can contact the Research Ethics Officer on (07) 3735 4375 or research-ethics@griffith.edu.au if you have any concerns about the ethical conduct of the project.
- Agree to participate in the project

Name

Signature

Date / /